

LONG-TERM INTERFACIAL PERFORMANCE OF SURFACE TREATED CFRP COMPOSITES UNDER HYGROTHERMAL CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites have attracted much attention because of their high specific mechanical properties. A promising application of CFRP is in marine and offshore area, where the satisfactory long-term performance of the composite is highly depending on the interfacial/interlaminar properties and matrix degradation due to moisture intake. The aim of this work is to study the effect of moisture absorption and surface treatment of fiber on the interfacial properties of CFRP. Multiwalled carbon nanotubes were incorporated into the silane coating on fiber surface to enhance the interfacial bonding of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite and the composites were exposed to de-ionized water and simulated seawater. The results of the microbond tests showed that the interfacial shear strength of the hybrid composites can be obviously increased in comparison with the common composite. In the hybrid composites, the chemical bonding introduced by silane coating plays a leading role in reinforcing the interphase, and the addition of carbon nanotubes leads to a considerable further enhancement. Salt ions slowed down the speed and reduced the amount of water absorption in the beginning stage while had little effect on the finally stable IFSS of the composites after long-term water immersion. Hygrothermal effects on CFRP laminates were also investigated. interlaminar shear strength (ILSS), mode I and mode II interlaminar fracture toughness of the laminates decreased under hygrothermal environment. Silane treatment improved the interlaminar fracture toughness of laminates and incorporation of MWCNTs further enhanced these interfacial properties. The study concludes that deionized water and simulated seawater have similar long-term effect on interfacial performance of CFRP composites and surface treatment can enhance the interfacial bonding between carbon fiber and epoxy in both dry and long-term hygrothermal environments.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites are widely used in marine and offshore area recently because of their superior specific mechanical properties. For safety and long term working efficiency, their resistance to environmental exposure attracts much attention [1]. Since moisture and heat may degrade the mechanical properties of CFRP, especially which are related to fiber-matrix interface, it is of great importance to investigate the hygrothermal effects on CFRP and improve the interfacial resistance of composites to environment. To improve fiber matrix bonding strength, many methods were developed to modify both carbon fibers and matrix, such as fiber sizing and coating, electrochemical oxidation, liquid-phase chemical oxidation and incorporating nanofillers into matrix directly. A new method emerged very recently that sizing doped with nanofillers can be applied onto carbon fibers to enhance the interphase between carbon fibers and matrix [2]. Moisture is unfriendly to

polymer composites, and could cause polymer debond from fibers. Complete immersion in water constitutes the most sever environment and also is the real condition where offshore structures work. Under high temperature, the moisture diffusion rates can be accelerated and effect of water on the interfacial properties of CFRP can be drawn within a shorter time [3, 4].

In the present paper, MWCNTs were dispersed in silane coupling agent and then the solution was applied to the carbon fiber. The hygrothermal effects on different treated CFRP composites were compared. Interfacial shear strength, Mode I and Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness and interlaminar shear strength of CFRP were evaluated using microbond tests, double cantilever beam (DCB) tests, end-notch flexure tests (ENF) and short beam shear (SBS) tests, respectively. The reinforcement mechanisms were analysed according to the characterization of fractured surface morphology and glass transition temperature variation.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Commercially available HexTow IM2C carbon fibre cloth with an average diameter of approximately 5.2 μm in a 2-2 twill configuration, were used as the primary reinforcement. The epoxy matrix, Epolam 5015 resin, is a mixture of Bisphenol F and Bisphenol A resins supplied by Axson Technologies. The Epolam 5015 hardener consists of isophoronediamine and polyoxypropylenediamine. (3-glycidyloxypropyl) trimethoxysilane coupling agent was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. Nanocyl NC7000 multiwalled carbon nanotubes were used as the secondary reinforcement. The average diameter and length of NC7000 CNTs are 9.5 nm and 1.5 μm , respectively. Seawater was simulated by dissolving sea salt (SIEM Trading PTE Ltd) in tap water to make a 3.5% salinity solution. All chemicals in this study were used without further purification unless otherwise specified.

2.2 Preparation of samples

For the microbond tests, three composite systems with different surface treatments are compared and two moisture conditions are imposed to those composites, as listed in Table 1. The microbond specimens and pure epoxy plates were immersed in de-ionized water and simulated seawater for up to 120 days at ambient temperature.

The preparation of coating solution and working mechanism of silane coupling agent has been discussed in detail in previous paper [5]. A mixture of ethanol and water with ratio of 95:5 was prepared and PH value was adjusted to 5. (3-glycidyloxypropyl) trimethoxysilane was then added into the solvent to yield a 2% final concentration. The introduction of MWCNTs with loading of 0.05 wt% into the solution was achieved by ultrasonicing for 30 minutes and then followed the same

Sample code	Fiber surface treatment	Water
CF-DIW	Non-treated	De-ionized water
SL-CF-DIW	Silane treated original CF	De-ionized water
CNT/SL-CF-DIW	CNT modified silane treated original CF	De-ionized water
CF-SW	Non-treated	Seawater
SL-CF-SW	Silane treated original CF	Seawater
CNT/SL-CF-SW	CNT modified silane treated original CF	Seawater

Table 1: Sample codes for the composite systems with two kinds of fiber surface treatment method and immersed in the two water environments

procedure. After the solution has been prepared, the carbon fibers were then soaked in the silane coupling agent solution (with or without MWCNTs) for several minutes followed by drying at 110°C for 20 minutes.

The carbon-epoxy composites laminates were manufactured using Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Moulding (VARTM) process. Peel-ply was added above these layers and finally an infusion mesh was added on top of the peel-ply to aid the wet out of the fibers. The epoxy resin was fed into the vacuum bag with a PVC hose and infusion spiral until fully distributed within the layers. This set up can be seen in Fig. 1a and b. The laminate was left to cure at room temperature for 24 hours and then post cured at 80 °C for 16 hours. The average thickness of the samples was measuring around 3.0 mm. The specimens were then immersed in tap water for up to 60 days at 80°C. For easier discussion, the as received, silane coupling agent treated and CNTs modified silane treated composites are defined as CF, SL-CF and CNT/SL-CF.

2.3 Characterization and mechanical tests

The surface topography of fractured specimens was characterized by field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM, JEOL JSM 6700F).

Microbond test was carried out using an in-house developed tester equipped with a 250 gram force load cell. The details of the device and testing parameters can be found in our previous work [5]. The interfacial shear strength (IFSS) τ was determined using the equation below, assuming the interfacial shear stress keeps constant along the fiber:

$$\tau = \frac{F}{\pi D l} \quad (1)$$

where F is the maximum pull out force, D is the fiber diameter, l is the embedded length. For each data point, more than 20 valid testing results were collected in order to offset the scattering of the measured results.

The Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of the samples was determined in accordance with the ASTM D5528-01. The dimension of composite laminates for DCB tests was 157.5 mm × 25 mm with the starter crack length of 57.5 mm. To prepare the samples for loading, the edges of the samples were coated with a thin layer of water-based correction fluid ahead of the insert and vertical lines were drawn every 1 mm in order to aid the visualization of crack propagation. The double cantilever beam test was performed using Instron 5569 universal testing machine at crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. The modified beam compliance theory was used to calculate Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness using the following equation:

$$G_{IC} = \frac{3P_c \delta_c}{2B(a + \Delta)} \quad (2)$$

where G_{IC} is the Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, P_c is the critical loading value, δ_c is the deflection value, B is the specimen width and a is the crack length, Δ is correction factor to account for rotation of the DCB arms. It is determined experimentally by generating a least squares plot of the cube root of compliance ($C^{1/3}$) as a function of delamination length, where C is δ_c/P_c . The crack initiation value of $G_{IC(init)}$ is defined using the load and deflection measured at the point at which delamination is visually observed on the edge. As to the mode I propagation fracture toughness, G_{IC} usually increases firstly and then reaches a plateau. The crack propagation value $G_{IC(prop)}$ used here is the average of the plateau values.

The dimension of composite laminates for ENF tests was 70 mm × 10 mm with the starter crack length of 20 mm and the effective span length of 60 mm. To determine the Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{IIC}) of the samples, an ENF test was performed using an Instron 5569 universal testing machine with crosshead speed of 2 mm/min at room temperature. The Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness was determined for each specimen using the following equation [6]:

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{9a^2 P_c \delta_c}{2B(2L^3 + 3a^3)} \quad (3)$$

where a is the crack length, P_c is the critical loading value, δ_c is the specimen deflection value, B is the specimen width and L is half of the span length. Since in the ENF test, the crack growth is unstable, only crack initiation $G_{IIc(Init)}$ values can be obtained.

Interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of the samples was determined in accordance with the ASTM D2344/D2344M-00 standard using three-point short beam shear test. Dimension of composite laminates for SBS tests was 18 mm × 9 mm in size. The test was performed using an Instron 5569 universal testing machine at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. The ILSS values were determined using the following equation:

$$ILSS = 0.75 \times \frac{P_m}{b \times h} \quad (4)$$

where P_m is the maximum load, b is the specimen width and h is the specimen thickness.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microbond test

Table 2 lists the IFSS values determined at the 0th, the 20th, and the 120th day. The IFSS of SL-CF-DIW system remains 14.8% improvement at the 20th day and 12.3% at the 120th day compared with CF-DIW system. For CNT/SL-CF-DIW system, the maintained improvement in IFSS are 23.0% (at the 20th day) and 21.6% (at the 120th day), respectively. In simulated seawater, SL-CF system remains the enhancement in IFSS of 10.7% at the 20th day and 11.9% at the 120th day. For CNT/SL-CF system, the maintained enhancements are 18.3% and 20.7% during the immersion test. The results indicate that though the IFSS decreases with immersion time, the surface treatments do not aggravate deterioration of interfacial properties in both water systems. It is noteworthy that all of the three composite systems maintain more interfacial shear strength in de-ionized water than in simulated seawater in the early stage of immersion test, though the water gain of epoxy in de-ionized water is faster than that in simulated seawater. Nevertheless, the difference becomes less and less with immersion time, and finally disappears after 100 day, which may imply that salt ions in seawater do not have additional long-term influence on the interfacial bonding of CFRP. The similar phenomenon is also observed by other researchers [7-9]. Liao et al. [7] found that salt concentration did not seem to affect flexural properties of E-glass fiber reinforced vinylester matrix composite in a noticeable way. Grant et al. [8] compared transverse tensile properties of three graphite/epoxy composite materials and found little difference in the behavior of those composites immersed in distilled water and in seawater. In the study reported by Davies et al. [9], the glass reinforced composites show the almost same shear strength after immersion in different water systems.

Sample code	IFSS (MPa)		
	0 day	20 days	120 days
CF-DIW	83.8±11.0	76.5±7.8	73.1±10.3
SL-CF-DIW	96.0±17.8 (14.6%)	87.8±14.6 (14.8%)	82.1±14.5 (12.3%)
CNT/SL-CF-DIW	105.9±12.4 (26.4%)	94.1±16.8 (23.0%)	88.9±8.9 (21.6%)
CF-SW	83.8±11.0	75.9±16.2	73.1±12.1
SL-CF-SW	96.0±17.8 (14.6%)	84.0±12.6 (10.7%)	81.8±15.6 (11.9%)
CNT/SL-CF-SW	105.9±12.4 (26.4%)	89.8±10.8 (18.3%)	88.2±10.5 (20.7%)

Note: Values in parentheses are increased percentages using CF-DIW and CF-SW samples as benchmarks.

Table 2: Interfacial shear strength of the three composite systems during the immersion tests

3.2 Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness

The mode I fracture toughness was evaluated using Eq. (2) at each water exposure interval. Fig. 1a shows typical load-displacement curves for three composite systems (CF, SL-CF, CNT/SL-CF). The G_{IC} values of crack initiation and propagation for each treatment type are shown in Fig. 1b and c. The $G_{IC(init)}$ value shows an increase of 22.4% when carbon fibers are treated with silane and 35.4% when CNTs are incorporated into the silane coating. After a 60 days hygrothermal treatment, the $G_{IC(init)}$ of the SL-CF and CNT/SL-CF specimens still show a 17.8% and 33% increase when being compared with the non-treated ones. There is a strange decrease of $G_{IC(init)}$ after 30 days treatment for CNT/SL-CF treated specimens, which may be due to the sample preparation errors. The increase of $G_{IC(init)}$ for silane treated CFRP composites is mainly due to the increased bonding strength between the fiber surface and the epoxy matrix. The silane coating can react with original sizing on carbon fibers on one side and form chemical bonding with epoxy matrix on the other side [5]. The CNT/SL-CF samples provide the highest $G_{IC(init)}$ and maintain high fracture toughness even after lengthy exposure to moisture. When CNTs are incorporated, thin layer of nanotube at the interface offers the opportunity for direct interaction both with the epoxy matrix and the carbon fiber when functional groups are available. Such interaction will directly affect interphase formulation of composites, and improve fracture toughness by CNTs bridging or CNTs pull-out [10, 5]. In addition, CNTs act as interlocking pins and could increase the friction at the interphase area. The high stiffness of CNTs can also ameliorate the stress concentration and help stress transfer from fibers to matrix.

SEM micrographs of the fractured surfaces of the carbon fibers under different treatments are shown in Fig. 2. It can be seen that the CF samples have very smooth surface (Fig. 2a), while both the SL-CF and CNT/SL-CF samples show much rougher surfaces (Fig. 2c) and (Fig. 2e and g), respectively. The smooth surface of the CF samples implies that at point of failure, the matrix is broken away from the fibers due to poor adhesion, whereas the addition of both silane and CNTs improve the adhesive properties and so a considerable amount of matrix remains intact after delamination, resulting in higher fracture toughness values as a greater load is required to break the interfacial bonds for these samples. After 60 days exposure, the resin in the CF samples (Fig. 2b) and SL-CF samples (Fig. 2d) can be seen to have broken down and the CNT/SL-CF samples (Fig. 2f and h) show weaker bonding between the matrix and fibers when being compared with dry samples, giving a smoother appearance in the SEM micrograph. So it can be confirmed that the presence of water aids in the deterioration of the interfacial properties and therefore the weakening of the composites.

Fig. 1(c) shows the values of $G_{IC(prop)}$. The carbon fiber surface treatment by MWCNTs modified silane coating decreases the crack propagation fracture toughness $G_{IC(prop)}$ significantly and hygrothermal effects on this kind of specimen are not obvious. However, under hygrothermal environment, $G_{IC(prop)}$ of the other two types of composites all increase firstly and then decrease. The crack propagation resistance $G_{IC(prop)}$ is highly influenced by the bridging effect of individual carbon fibers [11]. For the non-treated carbon fibers, they are separated heavily after DCB tests, which means fiber bridging effects happen easily (Fig. 2a and b). Surface modification using silane and MWCNTs reduces the effect of fiber-bridging and causes the dramatic decrease of crack propagation toughness. When MWCNTs modified silane coating is applied onto the carbon fibers, the fibers are prone to be bundled together and the bonding strength between carbon fibers and epoxy matrix improved drastically. As a result, the fibers are hard to be separated from each other (Fig. 2e and f), which makes fiber bridging difficult. Only silane treatment can also improve the bonding strength to some extent but not as obvious as silane plus MWCNT treatment. So, the $G_{IC(prop)}$ value is in between the other two kinds of specimens. Under hygrothermal environment, $G_{IC(prop)}$ of CF and SL-CF specimens all increase firstly and then decrease. The CF specimens reached the paramount point faster because of their poor interfacial bonding strength. Water is easy to penetrate into the composites from the interface and exacerbate the bridging effect. However, too much absorbed water can also weaken the interfacial bonding strength and pure epoxy strength, which may offset the bridging effect. As a result, the $G_{IC(prop)}$ decreases after certain time of immersion into the water. As to the SL-CF specimens, chemical bonds from surface treatment may ameliorate the negative effect of water on interfacial properties and weaken the bridging effect. So the highest values of $G_{IC(prop)}$ are smaller and reached

more slowly. When CNTs are incorporated into silane coating, the existence of CNTs improves the interfacial bonding between carbon fiber and epoxy matrix heavily. As a result, fibers are still bonding together even after 60 days hydrothermal treatment (as shown in Fig. 2e and f) and fiber bridging effects don't take place.

Figure 1: (a) Typical load-displacement curves of Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness test; (b) $G_{IC(init)}$ of different CFRP composites immersed in water for certain days; (c) $G_{IC(prop)}$ of different CFRP composites immersed in water for certain days.

Figure 2: SEM images of fractured surfaces of composites conditioned in water after DCB tests: (a) original specimens before immersion; (b) original specimens immersed for 120 days; (c) silane treated specimens before immersion; (d) silane treated specimens immersed for 120 days; (e) silane + CNT treated specimens before immersion; (f) silane + CNT treated specimens immersed for 120 days; (g) silane + CNT treated specimens before immersion (high magnification); (h) silane + CNT treated specimens immersed for 120 days (high magnification).

3.2 Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness

The mode II fracture toughness was evaluated using Eq. (3) and Fig. 3a shows typical load-displacement curves for three composite systems (CF, SL-CF, CNT/SL-CF). The average values of $G_{IIC(init)}$ for each treatment and water exposure interval are shown in Fig. 3b. There is a clear improvement seen in the mode II fracture toughness of the SL-CF and CNT/SL-CF samples. Before hydrothermal treatment, $G_{IIC(init)}$ of the SL-CF samples shows an improvement on the CF samples by 10.8%, whereas the $G_{IIC(init)}$ of the CNT/SL-CF samples is higher than the SL-CF samples by 19.9%. After being exposed in water for 60 days, the CNT/SL-CF samples still show higher $G_{IIC(init)}$ even when compared with dried CF samples.

Figure 3: (a) Typical load-displacement curves of Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness test; (b) $G_{IIc(init)}$ of different CFRP composites immersed in water for certain days.

Figure 4: Fracture surfaces of composites conditioned in water after ENF tests: (a) original specimens before immersion; (b) original specimens immersed for 120 days; (c) silane treated specimens before immersion; (d) silane treated specimens immersed for 120 days; (e) silane + CNT treated specimens before immersion; (f) silane + CNT treated specimens immersed for 120 days; (g) silane + CNT treated specimens before immersion (high magnification); (h) silane + CNT treated specimens immersed for 120 days (high magnification).

The fractured surfaces after ENF tests are shown in Fig. 4. The figures are similar to those of Mode I specimens. It can be seen that, before hygrothermal treatments, the CF samples have a relative smooth surface (Fig. 4a), while the other two kinds of samples show much rougher surfaces (Fig. 4c) and (Fig. 4e and g), respectively. After being immersed into hot water, the fractured surfaces of three types of composites all become smoother than before (as shown in Fig. 4b, d, f and h), which implies that hygrothermal treatments have negative effects on the interfacial bonding of CFRP. In Fig. 4g and h, CNTs can be clearly observed well dispersed on the surface of a carbon fiber; the matrix has been peeled away from the fiber but the process is somewhat resisted by the CNTs. These results imply the bonding strength is improved after surface treatments. These images help to explain the interfacial interactions between the fiber and CNT despite the low CNT loading within the silane solution. The reinforcing and hygrothermal resistant mechanism of both silane and MWCNTs are similar with the Mode I fracture toughness tests as the above mentioned.

3.2 Interlaminar shear strength

The interlaminar shear strength of the samples was evaluated using Eq. (4) for each of the water exposure intervals, as shown in Fig. 5b. The SBS tests give accurate measures of the ILSS value only if pure interlaminar shear failures take place. Fig. 5a shows typical load-displacement curves for three composite systems (CF, SL-CF, CNT/SL-CF). Fig. 6a shows an optical microscope image of a sample that has undergone interlaminar shear failure in the neutral plane due to maximum shear stress which

is the ideal failure mode for the SBS samples. However, the specimen usually encounters other types of damage before or concurrent with interlaminar shear failure, causing the specimen to fail by other than pure interlaminar shear [12-14]. Fig. 6b shows a mixed failure mode, whereby the onset of cracking was initiated outside of the neutral plane and propagate at a 90° orientation. This type of failure mode yields unreliable results for ILSS tests, as other failure modes are dominant over interlaminar shear. Fig. 5a also shows a typical failed load-displacement curve of interlaminar shear strength test (green color). Only if the load drops obviously immediately after the peak load is reached, it is assumed that the specimen failed in laminar shear [12]. Here in the tests, the peak load in this kind of circumstance was then used to determine the ILSS.

Figure 5: (a) Typical load-displacement curves of interlaminar shear strength test; (b) Interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of different CFRP composites immersed in water for certain days.

Figure 6: Optical microscope image of different failure modes after SBS tests: (a) interlaminar shear failure mode; (b) mixed failure modes.

The ILSS decreased continuously with the duration of submersion in the water bath. The increase of ILSS for silane treated CFRP is not obvious compared with CNT/SL-CF treated specimens. That is because the shear failure strength is not only influenced by interfacial properties of CFRP but also largely dependent on pure matrix properties [15]. Silane can only improve interfacial bonding strength to some extent, but not the epoxy matrix properties. So the effect of silane treatment is quite limited. However, the CNT/SL-CF composite system showed the best ILSS properties, which is 9% higher than CF specimens before hygrothermal treatments. After immersion in hot water, CNT/SL-CF samples still show a 4.3% higher ILSS than the non-treated samples. It indicates that this treatment has beneficial effects on the ILSS. Three possible mechanisms of CNTs for shear strength enhancement seem to work [10]. Firstly, nanotubes act like rigid fillers, which can toughen and reinforce the epoxy matrix at the interphase area by serving as a crack arrester and prevent expansion of microcracking. Secondly, nanotubes can improve the interfacial bonding strength of composites through the ‘‘bridging mechanism’’ in the resin-rich interphase area. In addition, the existence of CNTs can reduce the interlaminar stress concentration by smearing the mismatch of neighboring plies properties.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The interfacial bonding between the surface treated carbon fibers and epoxy matrix has been studied in the conditions imitating freshwater and marine environments through single fiber microbond

tests. Although the deterioration of interfacial shear strength in the different composites shows a similar trend during the immersion test, the composites using the carbon fibers with MWCNT-doped silane coating continuously maintain the improvement of interfacial shear strength compared to the composite using the as-received carbon fibers throughout the whole experiment. Furthermore, from a long-term point of view, one can expect that the effects of moisture in a marine environment on the degradation of interfacial bonding of CFRPs are similar to that in a freshwater environment. Silane coating and MWCNTs were also used to treat carbon fiber to compose hybrid CFRP composites. Effect of hygrothermal environment on mechanical properties of different treated CFRP was characterized. The analysis reveals that there are two main reinforcing mechanisms in the hybrid composites: by silane and CNTs. The addition of the silane coupling agent reveals an increase in all observed mechanical properties when being compared with CF samples. It has been established that the chemical bonding plays a significant role in this improvement. CNTs provide additional benefit by absorbing energy through their highly flexible elastic behavior during the deformation. It has also been found that for each modification, exposure to water results in adverse effects on all the mechanical properties. However, surface treatments can improve the hygrothermal resistance of CFRP and CNT/SL-CF specimens show the best results. The improvements observed as a result of this easy modification provides the potential use of silane and CNT modified composite laminates for large scale use in the marine industry.

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